

BIODIVERSITY AND ECOLOGICAL PROBLEMS

**Kurbanboyeva Bibijon Kurbanboy kizi
Yusupova Dilnoza Dilshodovna**

Professional University Navoi branch
Primary education 3rd year students.
kurbanboyevabibijon@gmail.com

yusupivadilnoza0705@gmail.com

Abstract: This thesis analyzes the role of biodiversity in nature and human life, its importance in maintaining the stability of ecosystems, and environmental problems that negatively affect biodiversity. The impact of climate change, environmental pollution, misuse of natural resources, desertification, and the Aral Sea ecological crisis on biodiversity is highlighted. Also, the relevance of protecting biological resources is revealed using the example of Uzbekistan. The thesis puts forward practical proposals and recommendations for preserving biodiversity.

Keywords: biodiversity, atmosphere, ecosystem, environmental problem, climate change, Aral Sea, desertification, pollution, protection, sustainable development.

Biodiversity refers to the variety of all living organisms in nature and the variety of natural environments in which they live. This concept is not limited to the flora and fauna, but also includes microorganisms, genetic resources and entire ecosystems. Biodiversity is the most important wealth of nature and is one of the main factors in ensuring the stability of ecosystems.

Biodiversity is also of great importance to human life. Humans get food, medicine, clean air, water, and many other natural resources from nature. Therefore, the decline in biodiversity directly affects the quality of human life. From this perspective, protecting biodiversity is not only ecological, but also economic and social. [United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). UNEP and Biodiversity] One of the biggest problems threatening biodiversity today is climate change. In recent years, global warming, drought, water shortages, and other natural disasters have been increasing. According to international data, about 1 million species in the world are at risk of extinction. [United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). Facts about the Nature Crisis.] This figure alone shows how serious the problem is. I believe that the loss of biodiversity will have serious consequences for humanity in the future, such as water shortages, reduced agricultural productivity, and an increase in natural disasters can cause. Another factor that negatively affects biodiversity is environmental pollution. Industrial enterprises, vehicles, household waste and chemicals pollute the air, water and soil. It is noted that 75 percent of the Earth's land surface has been significantly changed as a result of human activity. [United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). Facts about the Nature Crisis.] This indicator means that humans are interfering with nature excessively. If environmental responsibility in production and consumption is not increased today, the restoration of biological resources in the future will be even more difficult. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, the issue of biodiversity requires special attention. The Lower Amudarya Biosphere Reserve is one of the unique natural areas in Central Asia, and it is an important habitat for rare animals such as the Bukhara deer.

One of the most serious environmental problems in our country is the ecological crisis of the Aral Sea. The drying up of the Aral Sea has led to desertification, soil salinization, dust storms, and a reduction in biological resources. The "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy sets the task of creating a green cover on an area of 1.3 million hectares on the dried-up bottom of the Aral Sea. [Government of Uzbekistan. Ecological goals under the Uzbekistan-2030 strategy.

This measure will also serve to restore biodiversity. To preserve biodiversity, it is necessary to strengthen environmental education, rational use of resources, reduce waste, and expand protected areas. I think that every citizen is also responsible in this matter.

In this regard, it is worth noting that the Decree of our Honorable President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev dated April 21, 2017 No. PF-5024 on improving the state management system in the field of ecology and environmental protection, the current Resolution No. PQ-2915 on measures to improve the activities of the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan for Ecology and Environmental Protection, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers and the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers dated May 23, 2017 No. 310, the Regulation on the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan for Ecology and Environmental Protection [Ecology Bulletin. No. 5 (193) 2017] are of great importance in resolving the above-mentioned issues. In the current conditions of globalization, increasing competition requires the development and implementation of a completely new approach and principles for the more stable and rapid development of our state. [Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. "Voice of Uzbekistan", February 9, 2017]

In conclusion, biodiversity is the most important wealth of nature and the basis of ecological sustainability. Currently, climate change, environmental pollution, desertification and the Aral Sea crisis pose a serious threat to biodiversity. Therefore, the protection of biological resources, the promotion of ecological culture and the development of green technologies are among the urgent tasks of today.

List of used literature:

1. United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). UNEP and Biodiversity
2. United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). Facts about the Nature Crisis.
3. United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). Facts about the Nature Crisis.
4. UNESCO. Lower Amudarya State Biosphere Reserve.
5. Government of Uzbekistan. Ecological objectives of the Uzbekistan-2030 strategy.
6. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan". "Voice of Uzbekistan", February 9, 2017.
7. Ecology. Q.Kh. Muftaydinov, H.M. Kodirov, E.Yu. Yulchiyev Tashkent 2020
8. Ecology Bulletin. No. 5 (193) 2017